

Assessment Questionnaire

A.1 Prologue

Although process modeling and user stories are potentially related, this relationship is often not explored in a way that truly benefits software development in an agile context. This issue highlights the need for a solution that ensures traceability between business processes and their respective requirements. The objective of this questionnaire is to validate transformation patterns that derive user stories and scenarios from BPMN business process models.

The extraction results come from a transformation tool developed as part of a research project. Thus, within this context, the extracted information consists of a set of user stories using the template, or variations thereof: "**As a** «*Role*», **I want to** «*Task*» **in order to** «*Goal*»". For cases with alternative flows, scenarios using the "**Given-When-Then**" template from the Gherkin syntax [1] will be used.

Below is a practical example of a scenario using the mentioned template:

Scenario: Dr. Bill posts to his own blog

Given I am logged in as Dr. Bill

When I try to post to "Expensive Therapy"

Then I should see "Your article was published."

A.2 Background and Identification

1. How many years of experience do you have in process modeling?

- A. Less than 1
- B. Between 1 and 5
- C. Between 6 and 10
- D. More than 10

2. How many years of experience do you have in the field of Requirements Engineering?

- A. Less than 1
- B. Between 1 and 5
- C. Between 6 and 10
- D. More than 10

3. Which of these agile methodologies have you worked with?

- A. SCRUM
- B. Extreme Programming (XP)
- C. Kanban
- D. Lean Development
- E. Crystal
- F. Other: _____

4. How would you rate your experience with user story analysis?

- A. I have never had contact
- B. I understand the concept theoretically
- C. I am comfortable with simple analysis
- D. I can perform detailed analysis

A.3 Analysis of Extractions

Please, with regard to the following model, answer each set of questions related to the user stories and Gherkin scenarios extracted from the respective models presented before the questions.

A.3.1 Goods shop store model

Figure A.3.1: Goods shop store model.

User Stories A.3.1:

- US1. As Goods Shop Store I receive a(n) Order in order to Process Order.
- US2. As Goods Shop Store I want to Produce Fresh Product in order to Ship Order.
- US3. As Client I want to send Order in order to get Order Processed.
- US4. As Goods Shop Store, I want to execute Organize Shipment, Package Goods, together.

A.3.2 Identify Appointment fragment expanded with the characteristics of a check-in

Figure A.3.2: Identify Appointment fragment expanded with the characteristics of a check-in, adapted from [2].

User Stories A.3.2:

- US1. As Reception I receive a(n) Request in order to Retrieve Appointment.
- US2. As Customer I want to send Request in order to get Appointment Details.

Scenarios A.3.2:

Scenario 1: Reception get Request With Appointment? leads to no

Given Request made
When Request With Appointment? leads to no
Then Reception Specify Stay.

Scenario 2: Reception Check Availability

Given Check Availability made
When Do you want to wait? leads to no
Then Reception sends Unavailability.

1. How accurate was the extraction of user stories, based on the model presented?
 - A. Does not correspond to the model
 - B. Not very representative of the model
 - C. Positive but needs some corrections
 - D. Accurate extraction, may need slight adjustments

A.3.3 CP (segment) for the psycho-oncological service

Figure A.3.3: CP (segment) for the psycho-oncological service, adapted from [3].

User Stories A.3.3:

- US1. As Doctor I receive a(n) Consultation Request in order to Ccheck if a conversation is possible.
- US2. As Doctor I want to Service introduces and explain reason for the visit in order to Get the patient's consent.
- US3. As Doctor I want to Complete consultation paper in order to send Consultation paper to prehospital and inpatient diagnostics or surgical treatment or chemotherapy depending on Where to send consultation paper?.
- US4. As Prehospital and inpatient diagnostics I want to send Consultation Request in order to get Consultation paper.
- US5. As Doctor, I will follow one or more of these paths: option 1, option 4, option 3, option 2 in order to execute one or more of the respective activities: Accomplish imagination exercises, Have a diagnostic interview, Have a counseling interview, Have an exit interview.

1. How accurate was the extraction of user stories, based on the model presented?

- A. Does not correspond to the model
- B. Not very representative of the model
- C. Positive but needs some corrections
- D. Accurate extraction, may need slight adjustments

2. How accurate was the extraction of the scenarios based on the model presented?

- A. Does not correspond to the model
- B. Not very representative of the model
- C. Positive but needs some corrections
- D. Accurate extraction, may need slight adjustments

3. Are there any user stories or scenarios you disagree with? If yes, which ones?

4. What changes would you make to the extracted content (user stories and scenarios)?

Figure A.3.4: Property Valuation, adapted from [4]

User Stories A.3.4:

- US1. As Customer service I receive a(n) Evaluation request in order to Register Documentation.
- US2. As Judicial I want to Check Documentation in order to Customer service can Schedule evaluation.
- US3. As Customer service I want to send a(n) Notification of evaluation date to Owner, considering that I have to wait for Date and time of the evaluation in order to Brokerage can Evaluate property.
- US4. As Brokerage I want to Suggest value in order to send Property (evaluated) to Owner.
- US5. As Owner I want to send Evaluation request in order to get Property (evaluated).

Scenarios A.3.4:

Scenario 1: Judicial Check Documentation leads to irregular

Given Judicial made Check Documentation

When Check Documentation leads to irregular

Then Judicial sends Notification of irregularity.

Scenario 2: Judicial Notification of irregularity After 30 days without answer

Given Judicial send Notification of irregularity

When After 30 days without answer

Then Judicial sends Notification of interruption.

Scenario 3: Brokerage Irregularity found in Evaluate property

Given Brokerage starts Evaluate property

When Irregularity found in Evaluate property

Then Brokerage sends Notify irregularity.

1. How accurate was the extraction of user stories, based on the model presented?
 - A. Does not correspond to the model
 - B. Not very representative of the model
 - C. Positive but needs some corrections
 - D. Accurate extraction, may need slight adjustments
2. How accurate was the extraction of the scenarios based on the model presented?
 - A. Does not correspond to the model
 - B. Not very representative of the model
 - C. Positive but needs some corrections
 - D. Accurate extraction, may need slight adjustments

3. Are there any user stories or scenarios you disagree with? If yes, which ones?

4. What changes would you make to the extracted content (user stories and scenarios)?

A.4 Overview

1. What level of usefulness is attributed to this extraction prototype, in the context of eliciting and specifying requirements?

- A. Nothing useful
- B. Regular
- C. Interesting
- D. Very useful

2. As a business process designer or requirements engineer, would you use this approach?

- A. Always
- B. In most models
- C. Only in specific cases
- D. Never

Reference

- [1] S. Software. Cucumber Docs. Acedido a Jul 25, 2023. url: <https://cucumber.io/docs>.
- [2] M.L.F. Albuquerque; C.S. Lopes; D.S. da Silveira. Mutatis mutandis: An abstraction with reusable building block used to teach business process modeling. In: Journal of Education for Business 98.2 (2023), pp. 95–105.
- [3] H. Scheuerlein *et al.* New methods for clinical pathways—business process modeling notation (BPMN) and tangible business process modeling (t. BPM). In: Langenbeck's archives of surgery 397 (2012), pp. 755–761.
- [4] V. Mendoza; D.S. da Silveira; M.L. Albuquerque; J. Araújo. Verifying BPMN understandability with novice business managers. In Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing (SAC '18). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, pp. 94–101. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3167132.3167139>.